

Comparison of ultrasound to MR and histological methods for liver fat quantification

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This prospective pilot study aims to evaluate the capabilities of novel quantitative ultrasound (QUS) methods based on attenuation (Att.PLUS) and sound speed (SSp.PLUS) for detecting liver fat.

Patients and methods: The study included 56 individuals with biopsy-proven steatosis (percutaneous liver biopsy) ranging from 0 % to 90 % of hepatocytes containing intracellular lipid vacuoles. Histopathology was considered reference standard. Abdominal QUS examinations were conducted using Att.PLUS and SSp.PLUS techniques on the Aixplorer MACH 30 system. Comparative assessments were made using the results of liver biopsy and magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) together with magnetic resonance imaging proton density fat fraction (MRI-PDFF). MR examinations were performed on the Siemens VIDA 3 T system.

Results: ROC analysis was conducted for two groups: (a) patients without steatosis (S0) versus those with steatosis (S1 + S2 + S3) yielded AUC values of 0.79 for Att.PLUS and 0.78 for SSp.PLUS, in contrast to an AUC > 0.95 for MRS and MRI-PDFF; and (b) patients without or with mild steatosis (S0 + S1) versus those with severe steatosis (S2 + S3), yielded AUC values of 0.93 for Att.PLUS and 0.89 for SSp.PLUS, in contrast to an AUC > 0.99 for MRS and MRI-PDFF. However, MR methods were superior in detecting liver fat content in obese patients and post-liver transplantation individuals.

Conclusion: Both QUS parameters (Att.PLUS and SSp.PLUS) appear equivalent at differentiating S0 vs. (S1 + S2 + S3) patients, but the Att.PLUS parameter may be more effective at identifying advanced steatosis (S2 + S3). MR techniques outperformed QUS methods, making them more suitable for clinical studies.

1. Introduction

Following a nomenclature update in June 2023, the characterization of steatotic liver disease (SLD) now encompasses various causes of liver steatosis [1]. Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), formerly nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), closely linked to metabolic syndrome, is the predominant cause of chronic liver disease in Western countries, with global prevalence, ranging between 25 and 30 %, on the rise. In many countries, MASLD is the main reason for patients being placed on waiting lists for liver transplantation. MASLD includes individuals with hepatic steatosis and at least one of

five cardiometabolic risk factors. Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH) involves steatosis associated with inflammation and hepatocellular injury.

For many years, liver biopsy was considered the gold standard for fat quantification. Histological assessment and quantification of hepatic steatosis is based on the percentage of hepatocytes containing intracellular lipid vacuoles. While histological examination provides valuable information about steatosis, liver biopsy is invasive, poses risks to the patient, and provides only a limited amount of tissue for analysis. Non-invasive imaging methods, especially magnetic resonance imaging with proton density fat fraction (MRI-PDFF), and MR spectroscopy (MRS), are

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better alternatives [2]. MRI-PDFF, known for its high accuracy and ability to evaluate a broader area than biopsy, is considered the non-invasive reference standard.

The controlled attenuation parameter (CAP), measured using the FibroScan (Echosens, France) device, is the first non-invasive tool for quantifying hepatic steatosis based on US attenuation in the liver. However, as the accuracy of CAP in grading steatosis in MASLD patients is limited, it is not recommended as a reference standard for assessing quantitative ultrasound (QUS) methods [3,4].

New QUS methods [5], including the attenuation coefficient (AC), the speed of sound estimation (SoS) [6], are utilized in conventional B-mode. Clinical studies of the QUS methods available for measuring steatosis mostly relate to attenuation [7–11], providing good results. Attenuation parameters, widely used in clinical practice, can be measured using various methods. Over the past decade, several QUS techniques for measuring attenuation have been described, with a number of commercial instruments now providing quantitative measurements [5].

Clinical measurements of steatosis using AC have been published in a series of studies; cut-off mean, range and AUC values from a total of 16 papers are summarized in Table 1.

However, according to one recent study, the AC value is not only depth-dependent, but also affected by the size of the measurement box [18]. SoS is another emerging marker for quantifying liver fat content. Several animal and phantom studies along with several clinical studies consider sound speed estimation to be a promising clinical tool for measuring steatosis.

Both of these parameters, attenuation (Att.PLUS) and sound speed (SSp.PLUS), are measured using the Aixplorer MACH 30 system (SuperSonic Imagine, Aix-en-Provence, France) and, to our knowledge, two studies have been dedicated to their application [9,19]. AC and SoS are also available in US systems from other vendors.

This pilot study aimed to compare QUS methods for assessing steatosis based on the measurement of SoS and AC in routine clinical practice. Specifically, we compared these results with liver biopsies and liver fat content values obtained through MRS and MRI examinations. Our focus was exclusively on methods for liver fat quantification, irrespective of patients' diagnoses, comorbidities, or other relevant factors.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Patient selection

The study was performed on a group of subjects with varying liver fat content, ranging from nonsteatotic livers to subjects with severe steatosis. It was designed as a methodological study, and the cohort of patients does not represent the general population. However, no special inclusion or exclusion criteria were applied, except for contraindications to MR. The cohort consisted of patients referred for routine, everyday examinations, including both ultrasound and MR, specifically for liver fat measurement. Thirty liver transplant recipients and 30 patients scheduled for bariatric surgery (38 females/22 males, age 34–75 years, BMI 17.2–54.4 kg/m²), all of whom underwent clinical examination, were selected for liver biopsy, abdominal ultrasound (US) examination, and liver examination using magnetic resonance (MR) for the determination of liver fat fraction (FF) using MRS and MRI-PDFF. MR and US

Table 1

Summary of attenuation coefficients from the literature [5] (includes 8 references), [7,11–17].

Cut-off	(S0) vs. (S1 + S2 + S3)	(S0 + S1) vs. (S2 + S3)
Mean	0.642 ± 0.047	0.695 ± 0.045
Range	0.550–0.730	0.620–0.780
AUC	0.872 ± 0.050	0.905 ± 0.046

AUC: area under curve; S: grade of steatosis.

examinations were conducted on the same day following a fasting period of at least six hours.

Four patients refused liver biopsy; these data were excluded from our statistical calculations. Results from histology, MR and US were compared in 56 subjects. Three subjects were not examined by ultrasound due to technical reasons. Similarly, PDFF (VIBE_{whole}) results were not available in other three subjects. In all these cases, missing data points for Att.PLUS and SSp.PLUS, and VIBE_{whole} values, respectively, were imputed based on the mean values of the respective dataset.

Liver biopsies of patients after transplantation were mainly performed on the same day as MR and US (mean 0.7 days, range 0–7 days). Biopsies of patients undergoing bariatric surgery were performed during the operation; the period between MR and bariatric surgery was 17 days on average (range 1–70 days).

The examinations were approved by the local ethics committee of the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine and Thomayer Hospital in Prague in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. All subjects provided their written informed consent prior to the examinations.

2.2. Ultrasound

QUS examinations were performed using the Aixplorer MACH 30 system (SuperSonic Imagine, Aix-en-Provence, France) equipped with a 3.5 MHz abdominal curved transducer (SC6-1) and followed the WFUMB recommendations [5]. Two new QUS techniques, Sound Speed Plane-wave UltraSound (SSp.PLUS) and Attenuation Plane-wave UltraSound (Att.PLUS), were employed to detect liver steatosis. Both techniques are approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). SSp.PLUS measures the speed of sound (m/s) while Att.PLUS measures tissue ultrasound beam attenuation (dB/cm/MHz). Both modes are available in B-mode combined in a single acquisition.

Furthermore, Viscosity Plane-wave UltraSound (Vi.PLUS) (Pa.s) and ShearWave Elastography (2D-SWE.PLUS) for stiffness measurements (kPa) were also made.

Examination was performed during neutral respiratory apnoea from right intercostal view, US transducer was placed so that the hepatic capsule was parallel to the transducer on US image. The region of interest (ROI) with constant size, is set at a fixed distance from transducer (proximal part at 4 cm, distal part at 8 cm) and cannot be moved. Area of ROI was homogenous and free of large vessels, bile ducts and artifacts, see Fig. 1. For each patient, three acquisitions for each method were performed by the same physician with 20 years of experience in the US, who was unaware of the MR results. The vendor's application specialist trained the operator (H.G.) to use Att.PLUS and SSp.PLUS methods in everyday clinical practice, and these techniques have been used in our department since 2019. Quality control was done in accordance with the vendors' recommendations: a) the Stability Index (SI) was used to ensure accuracy, with each SWE measurement acquired with an SI above 90 %; b) a reliability criterion was set such that the ratio of the interquartile range to the median was less than 30 %.

2.3. MR imaging and MR spectroscopy

The MR examination was performed on the VIDA 3 T MR system (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany), equipped with a 30-channel surface body array coil and a 32-channel spine coil. Standard localization was done with the HASTE sequence (TR/TE = 1400/95 ms, 5 mm slice thickness). The liver fat fraction (FF) was determined using the HISTO MRS sequence (TR = 3000 ms; TEs = 12, 24, 36, 48, 72 ms) with a volume of interest measuring 40 x 30 x 25 mm in liver segments V/VIII. Additionally, two MRI sequences, T1 VIBE e-Dixon (TR/TE = 3.97/1.29 ms, resolution 1.2x1.2x3 mm) and VIBE q-Dixon (TR/TE = 9/1.05 ms, resolution 1.4x1.4x3.5 mm), were used to calculate liver volume and the amount of fat using the PDFF technique, both for the entire liver (VIBE_{whole}) and the HISTO position (VIBE_{roi}). All sequences were measured during breath expiration. Both imaging PDFF (2-echoes e-

Fig. 1. Attenuation (Att.PLUS) and Speed of Sound (SSp.PLUS) in patients without (left) and with (right) steatosis. MACH 30 US device, SuperSonic Imagine, Aix-en-Provence, France.

Dixon and 6-echoes q-Dixon) and spectroscopic FF (HISTO) measurements were performed using Siemens LiverLab protocol that includes sequences as well as evaluation algorithms calculating the fat content. For details, see the reference [20].

2.4. Histopathology

Samples for histological analysis were obtained by percutaneous non-targeted liver biopsy from the right lobe performed by hepatologists, and/or during bariatric surgery by the surgeon. The 16-gauge biopsy needle was used. To ensure uniform and representative sampling, the minimum inclusion criterion was one sample with a minimum length of 20 mm and more than 10 portal tracts. All samples were transferred immediately after collection to the pathology department, where they were fixed and prepared for evaluation (no longer than 6 h after collection).

Histological analysis was conducted by three expert histopathologists. Hepatic fat content was determined by estimating the percentage of hepatocytes containing intracellular lipid vacuoles using hematoxylin and eosin staining. Histopathology was considered the reference method for the measurement of the hepatic fat content in this study. A semi-quantitative scale with 5 % increments was used to describe the extent of the affected hepatocytes. Data were categorized using the histological scoring system for NAFLD [21] based on the following steatosis stages: S0 (no steatosis; < 5 % of hepatocytes affected), S1 (mild steatosis; 5–33 % of hepatocytes affected), S2 (moderate steatosis; 33–66 % of hepatocytes affected), and S3 (severe steatosis; > 66 % of hepatocytes affected). According to the NAFLD activity score (NAS), patients were defined as non-steatosis (NoS), NAFL (NAS 1–4 points), or NASH (NAS ≥ 5 points). Fibrosis staging was evaluated separately from NAS according to the histological scoring system for NAFLD.

2.5. Statistics

We used Microsoft Excel for data management and GraphPad Prism 10 (GraphPad Software, Boston, USA, <https://www.graphpad.com>) for statistical analysis. Metrics were determined based on P values < 0.05, which were considered statistically significant, and served as the threshold for confidence intervals. The results of the ROC analysis were characterized by the area under the curve (AUC), with cut points determined using the highest Youden index. AUC values were categorized as follows: excellent (0.9–1), good (0.8–0.9), fair (0.7–0.8), poor (0.6–0.7), and failed (0.5–0.6). Additional parameters were calculated to evaluate the separation of groups (S0) vs. (S1 + S2 + S3) and (S0 + S1) vs. (S2 + S3), including positive likelihood ratio (PLR+), negative likelihood ratio (PLR-), sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and accuracy.

Diagnostic performance was assessed based on critical values for PLR+: values > 10 indicate strong confirmation of disease, while values between 5 and 10 indicate moderate utility. For PLR-, values < 0.1 strongly rule out disease, while values between 0.1 and 0.2 indicate moderate diagnostic value. These metrics were determined to identify the best separation of the defined groups.

3. Results

The study evaluated 56 individuals with histopathological results, as shown in Table 2. The groups of transplanted patients and patients before bariatric treatment only differed in BMI and, consequently, in the hepatic fat content. As was mentioned in the introduction, this prospective pilot study was only focused on the comparison of the methods; thus, diagnoses, comorbidities, and laboratory tests were not taken into account with respect to the study objectives.

In the first step, MR and QUS methods with histopathology were compared using exploratory correlation analysis. Since the majority of the data sets did not follow Gaussian distribution, the Spearman correlation coefficient was calculated. Fig. 2 shows very strong correlations between histology and the following MR parameters: FF_{HISTO}, PDFF from the whole liver (VIBE_{whole}), and PDFF from a specific position in the liver (VIBE_{roi}) corresponding to the HISTO position, where the Spearman $r > 0.8$. However, the correlation between histology and the QUS parameters Att.PLUS and SSp.PLUS was slightly lower (Spearman $r < 0.73$). Nonetheless, an almost linear decrease in sound speed and an

Table 2
Results of histopathology and mean values of QUS parameters in all study patients.

Histology steatosis (% hepatocytes involved)	Number of patients
S0	17
S1	18
S2	6
S3	15
NAFLD activity score (NAS)	
0–2	33
3–4	9
5–8	14
QUS parameters	Mean values (standard deviation; range)
Liver stiffness (kPa)	6.2 (1.6; 3.9–12.3)
Viscosity (Pa.s)	2.2 (0.3; 1.7–3.2)
Attenuation (dB/cm/MHz)	0.47 (0.13; 0.24–0.79)
Sound speed (m/s)	1519 (39; 1439–1627)

QUS: quantitative ultrasound; NAFLD: nonalcoholic fatty liver disease; NAS: NAFLD Activity Score.

Fig. 2. The correlation table includes experimental parameters with a Spearman coefficient $|r| > 0.3$. NAS: NAFLD activity score; FF_{HISTO}: fat fraction measured by MR spectroscopy; VIBE_{roi} and VIBE_{whole}: proton density fat fraction measured by MR imaging; Att.PLUS: attenuation coefficient measured using MACH 30 US device; SSp.PLUS: sound speed measured using MACH 30 US device.

increase in attenuation with increasing liver fat is shown in Fig. 3, which is in agreement with results from several studies. No significant correlation with stiffness and viscosity was found (Spearman $r < 0.3$); these parameters were omitted from further data analysis.

The histological classification was compared with the results obtained from QUS and MR, using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis to determine diagnostic accuracy. Cut-off points were established for two groups: (a) patients without steatosis (S0) versus patients with steatosis (S1 + S2 + S3) and (b) patients without or with mild steatosis (S0 + S1) versus patients with severe steatosis (S2 + S3), representing common clinical scenarios. ROC curves are demonstrated in Fig. 4; results are summarized in Table 3.

The results indicate that MR parameters (FF_{HISTO}, VIBE_{roi}, VIBE_{whole}) demonstrate excellent diagnostic performance for distinguishing between subject groups (S0) vs. (S1 + S2 + S3) and (S0 + S1) vs. (S2 + S3), with AUC values consistently ≥ 0.95 . Notably, FF_{HISTO} achieves perfect

Fig. 3. Linear regression of the liver fat content of 56 subjects described by level of steatosis S0-S3 vs. attenuation coefficient Att.PLUS, and vs. sound speed SSp.PLUS. The regression for Att.PLUS is described by the equation $Y = 0.07807 \cdot X + 0.3730$ with an r^2 of 0.459, and SSp.PLUS by the equation $Y = -19.50 \cdot X + 1546$ with an r^2 of 0.342.

discrimination (AUC = 1.00) for the latter comparison. These high AUC values confirm the ability of MR parameters to effectively differentiate between subjects with varying degrees of hepatic steatosis. Additionally, MR-based methods achieve high sensitivity ($\geq 97\%$) and specificity ($\geq 93\%$), ensuring both strong detection and exclusion capabilities. Their diagnostic performance is further supported by $PLR+ > 10$, indicating a robust capacity to confirm steatosis, and $PLR- < 0.1$, underscoring their reliability in ruling out the condition.

In comparison, QUS parameters (Att.PLUS and SSp.PLUS) show good-to-very-good performance, with AUC values ranging from 0.78 to 0.93. While they do not achieve the same level of accuracy as MR-based methods, their performance is still clinically valuable, particularly in distinguishing higher liver fat content groups (S2 + S3). For instance, Att.PLUS reaches an AUC of 0.93 for the (S0 + S1) vs. (S2 + S3) comparison, highlighting its usefulness in identifying more advanced steatosis.

4. Discussion

In our pilot study, we evaluated liver fat content in a cohort of 56 individuals with histologically confirmed steatosis (grades S0–S3) using QUS. Specifically, we measured sound speed and attenuation using the algorithms SSp.PLUS and Att.PLUS, integrated into the ultrasound device Aixplorer SuperSonic MACH 30. Our findings were compared against MRI-PDFF and MRS-FF methods, revealing a strong agreement between histology and ultrasound results, as well as excellent consistency between histology and MRI-PDFF and MRS measurements of liver fat content in agreement with e.g. [22].

In literature, see Table 1, significantly different cut-off values can be observed for distinguishing between groups (S0) and (S1 + S2 + S3) with AC approximately 0.642 (dB/cm/MHz) and between (S0 + S1) and (S2 + S3) with AC approximately 0.695 (dB/cm/MHz). AUC values are generally higher for the classification of (S0 + S1) vs. (S2 + S3) than for (S0) vs. (S1 + S2 + S3), indicating that AC is more suitable for characterizing advanced steatosis at the (S2 + S3) level. These findings are consistent with our results, although our cut-off values are slightly lower than the average values reported in the literature. This inconsistency may be explained by variations in software algorithms and the composition of the studied groups.

The differentiation of various tissues based on sound speed is a well-established method based on studies involving phantoms and animal models resulting in the development of different measurement algorithms [23–26]. However, clinical applications for determining liver steatosis are rare. Imbault et al. [19] conducted a study using an algorithm based on maximizing the spatial coherence of backscattered signals from a virtual focal spot. This algorithm was adopted in the SSp.PLUS technique, which compared differences in sound speed in liver phantoms with and without simulated steatosis (CIRS and ATS phantoms). Subsequently, they studied 17 individuals with different degrees of steatosis. The study found a strong agreement with the results of liver fat determination using MRI-PDFF and histology, with an acceptable R^2 value of 0.691. Additionally, they demonstrated the ability of SSp.PLUS to significantly differentiate between healthy and diseased patients, achieving an AUC of 0.952 with a cut-off of 1555 m/s.

In a later study [27], they examined a group of 100 individuals with no steatosis and severe steatosis, where the SSp.PLUS ranged from 1450 m/s to 1625 m/s; these results were validated using several phantoms and PDFF measurements. Dioguardi Burgio et al. [9] conducted a study in which they analyzed sound speed data from 100 individuals divided into training and validation cohorts. They found that patients without steatosis (S0) had mean sound speed values of 1.570 ± 0.026 mm/ μ s in the training group and 1.568 ± 0.023 mm/ μ s in the validation group. In contrast, patients with S1–S3 steatosis had mean sound speed values of 1.521 ± 0.031 mm/ μ s and 1.514 ± 0.019 mm/ μ s ($P < 0.01$) in both groups, respectively. Similarly, Popa et al. [28] reported cut-off values < 1524 m/s for SSp.PLUS, distinguishing between (S0 + S1) and (S2 +

Fig. 4. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves describe the ability of MR and QUS methods to distinguish between groups of subjects. a) Separation of subjects in (S0 + S1) group from those in (S2 + S3) group. b) Differentiation between the (S0) group and the (S1 + S2 + S3) group. All ROC curves have an AUC

above 0.5 (see Table 3). FF_{HISTO}: fat fraction measured by MR spectroscopy; VIBE_{whole}: proton density fat fraction measured by MR imaging; Att.PLUS: attenuation coefficient measured using MACH 30 US device; SSp.PLUS: sound speed measured using MACH 30 US device.

Table 3
Results of ROC analysis.

Parameter	Att.PLUS (dB/cm/ MHz)	SSp. PLUS (m/s)	FF _{HISTO} (%)	VIBE _{roi} (%)	VIBE _{whole} (%)
STEATOSIS grade (S0) vs. (S1 + S2 + S3)					
AUC	0.79	0.78	0.98	0.96	0.95
Std. Error	0.06	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.03
95 % CI	0.66 to 0.91	0.65 to 0.91	0.94 to 1.00	0.91 to 1.00	0.89 to 1.00
P value	<0.0007	<0.0008	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Youden index %	47.6	59.0	90.5	77.1	79.0
CUT point	>0.515	<1531	>2.86	>2.4	>5.850
PLR+	8.14	3.21	14.56	4.86	12.85
PLR-	0.49	0.19	0.03	0.04	0.15
sensitivity %	54.3	85.7	97.1	77.1	85.7
specificity %	93.3	73.3	93.3	100.0	93.3
PPV	0.97	0.86	0.97	0.90	0.90
NPV	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.97
ACCU	0.62	0.82	0.96	0.91	0.90
STEATOSIS grade (S0 + S1) vs. (S2 + S3)					
AUC	0.93	0.89	1.00	0.99	0.99
Std. Error	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.01
95 % CI	0.87 to 0.99	0.81 to 0.97	0.99 to 1.00	0.96 to 1.00	0.98 to 1.00
P value	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Youden index %	78.1	68.6	97.1	94.3	90.0
CUT point	>0.460	<1518	>11.77	>9.2	>9.75
PLR+	4.57	4.44	14.99	17.51	10.00
PLR-	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
sensitivity %	100.0	90.48	100.0	100.0	100.0
specificity %	78.1	78.13	97.1	94.3	90.0
PPV	0.68	0.68	0.89	0.91	0.95
NPV	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.95
ACCU	0.85	0.84	0.96	0.96	0.97

PLR+ = sensitivity / (100 - specificity), PLR- = (1 - sensitivity) / specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) = TP / (TP + FP), negative predictive value (NPV) = TN / (TN + FN), accuracy (ACCU) = (TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN), where TP = true positives, FN = false negatives, TN = true negatives, FP = false positives.

S3) steatosis with corresponding sensitivity and specificity values of 75 % and 93.4 %, respectively. Control data were based on CAP values obtained from FibroScan. Cut-off values in all three studies are consistent with our findings. However, our results show higher AUC, specificity, and sensitivity for the separation between (S0) and (S1 + S2 + S3) groups.

Collin et al. [29] compared four QUS parameters – Att.PLUS, SSp.PLUS, CAP, and hepato-renal index (HRI) – in a group of 105 mostly obese patients with steatosis classified by MRI-PDFF. Surprisingly, the highest correlation between PDFF and QUS was found for HRI, with an AUC of 0.91. The correlation between PDFF and SSp.PLUS was satisfactory at an AUC of 0.73, a result that corresponds with other studies.

With regard to the calibration of QUS methods for assessing liver steatosis, the MR parameters FF and PDFF are considered the most suitable reference methods [2]. This is in agreement with our comparison of QUS with MR and histological data using ROC and correlation analysis. Our findings suggest that the MR method outperforms both studied QUS methods – Att.PLUS and SSp.PLUS – in characterizing steatosis.

Our MR results are in agreement with the latest meta-analysis of MR-PDFF studies, which summarize quantitative data from 22 studies and more than 2800 patients [30]. Cut-off values of PDFF in the meta-analysis show that values for separation steatosis S0 vs. S1 + S2 + S3 lie between 3.42 and 10.21, and S0 + S1 vs. S2 + S3 lie between 9.88 and 22.93. It is in agreement with our findings of all three MR methods used.

Similar PLR+ and PLR- values also support it.

The study has several limitations. The US examinations and evaluations were performed by only one physician, which aligns with the standard procedure of a routine ultrasound examination. The second limitation of the study relates to the nature of the patient group under investigation. All the patients included in the study underwent US examinations based on a general physician request to assess steatosis, which was subsequently used for further treatment or patient monitoring. The evaluation of the patients in the study was solely based on the results of steatosis determination using the ultrasound method, which were then compared with the results from histology and MR.

5. Conclusion

This study underscores the complementary roles of QUS and MR-based methods in diagnosing hepatic steatosis. QUS is a feasible, non-invasive, and cost-effective option for first-line care, particularly for distinguishing advanced steatosis (S2 and S3), making it valuable in resource-limited settings. MR-based methods, including PDFF and FF, provide superior diagnostic accuracy and are ideal for the detailed characterization of MASLD. Together, these techniques balance accessibility and precision to meet diverse clinical needs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Halima Gottfriedova: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Monika Dezortova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Petr Sedivy:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Dita Pajuelo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Martin Burian:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation. **Eva Sticova:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Olga Snizkova:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Eva Honsova:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Filip Dolecek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Milan Hajek:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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